

ON THE ISSUE OF DEFINING NEWS TEXT

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Abstrakt: Ushbu maqola jurnalistika va medialingvistikada tadqiqot ob'ekti bo'lgan yangiliklar va yangiliklar matnining ta'rifini ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolaning maqsadiga erishish uchun taqqoslash, tahlil qilish va sintez usullaridan foydalanilgan. Ushbu maqolaning natijalari yangiliklar matnlarining mohiyatini yanada to'liqroq tushunish imkonini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: yangiliklar, media matn, medialingvistika, jurnalistika.

Абстракт: В данной статье рассматривается определение понятия «новости» в журналистике и медиалингвистике. Для достижения поставленной цели были использованы методы сравнения, анализа и синтеза. Результаты данной статьи дают более полное представление о природе новостных текстов.

Ключевые слова: новости, медиатекст, медиалингвистика, журналистика.

Abstract: This article examines the definition of news and news text in journalism and mediallynguistics, where it is usually stated as the object of research. To achieve the aim of the article, comparison, analysis, and synthesis methods have been used. Findings demonstrate that research in journalism mostly covers the topic of news value and defines news as information that has novelty. Whereas mediallynguistics describes the format, specific sentence structure, and linguistic units of news. Combining these definitions, it was concluded that the definition given by journalists helps to choose what could be defined as news; in contrast, mediallynguistics studies the representation, format, and other linguistic features of that news. The results of this article give a more comprehensive understanding of the nature of news texts.

Key words: news, media text, mediallynguistics, journalism.

Introduction

The formation of media linguistics has a direct relationship with the development of new technologies that facilitate and spread mass media. Radio, television, and the Internet, which are becoming widely available nowadays, have changed the way people communicate. The omnipresence of the media, its enormous role in public life, as well

as the growing number of speeches and written statements in the mass media have attracted the attention of scientists not only in the social sciences but also in the philological sciences. Accordingly, at the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, there was a rapid development of linguistic research that focused on the language of the media. This interest led to the emergence of a new sub-discipline of linguistics that is named medialogistics. This new branch of linguistics studies the functioning of language in the field of mass communication [3]. Although the term “medialogistics” is an analogy to the German “medienlinguistik”, nowadays in modern English work it is being replaced gradually by the terms “media studies” and “media discourse analysis”.

Another interesting feature of medialogistics is noted by Tatyana Dobrosklonskaya, who writes that medialogistics combines the features of two scientific directions. On the one hand, it is based on the cumulative base of linguistic research, but on the other hand, it is incorporated into the general medialogy system, which broadly indicates a wide-ranging method for the analysis of cultural transmission in society and across societies. It is explained by the fact that it is impossible to describe the media without paying attention to the language they use, while analyzing the language of the media without taking into account extra-linguistic phenomena would be incomplete. However, Alexander Kiklevich includes medialogistics in pragmatics along with legal linguistics, Internet linguistics, theolinguistics, eurolinguistics, and ecolinguistics [5, p. 203].

Alexandra Kuznetsova defines media texts as works of pragmatic orientation that deliver socially significant, non-specialized information to an audience [6, p. 144]. A significant component of media linguistics' theory is comprised of a set of parameters specially designed for a thorough and coherent description of all possible types of media texts. So the central concept of a media text is supported by a stable system of parameters that allow us to describe and classify all texts functioning in mass media in terms of their production, distribution, verbal, and media characteristics. This system includes the following parameters: 1) Authorship (the text could be produced either by an individual or a news agency); 2) Type of production (oral—written); 3) Type of presentation (oral—written); 4) Media channel used for transmitting: the printed journals, TV, Radio, Internet; 5) Functional type or text genre: news, comment and analysis, features, advertising; 6) Topical affiliation (politics, business, culture,

education, sport, and other universal media topics, forming the content structure of everyday information flow).

The theoretical framework of media linguistics helps to solve this problem by offering a universal typological classification, encompassing the whole variety of media texts, and overcoming the challenge of the constant speech flexibility factor. This classification is based on the functional stylistic classification formulated by an outstanding Russian linguist, Viktor Vinogradov, and allows to single out the following four types of media texts: news, comment and analysis, features, and advertising texts [4, p. 130]. In this article, we will focus on the news type of media text since news text is the main unit of media text, which is usually difficult to define. To clarify its definition, we examine works in journalism and mediallynguistics, where news and news text are mostly researched. The aim of this article is to compare the definitions of the term “news” in the two related areas to find their joint points and give a more complete conception of news texts.

Method

During the research, an analysis method was used to collect information on the definitions of news in journalism and media linguistics. Using the comparison method, the general and distinctive nature of these definitions was derived. By using the synthesis method, the study results shaped a comprehensive definition of news.

Results and Discussion

Considering news as a special type of discourse, Teun van Dijk formulates an important conclusion regarding the entire corpus of mass communication texts. He believes that “the structures of media texts can be adequately understood only in one case: if we analyze them as a result of the cognitive and social activity of journalists in the production of texts and their meanings, as a result of the interpretation of texts by newspaper readers and television viewers, based on the experience of their communication with the media” [8, p. 123].

News in Journalism

Lazutina notes that “news in its original meaning is not a genre of journalistic work but a new fragment of reality that changes the usual course of things and therefore requires public attention” [7, p. 128]. It is told not only about defining the concept of “news” for standardization but also about the author, who selects what news to present in the media. Indeed, hundreds of different events occur in the world every day, but

only some of them are covered by the media. Only those messages that have “news value” appear on newspaper pages and television screens. According to an American media specialist, the standard criteria for a news value degree should cover at least one of these topics: 1) conflict (tension, surprise); 2) development (triumph achievement); 3) catastrophe (defeat, destruction); 4) consequences (impact on society); 5) celebrity (social or political figure); 6) novelty (unusual, even extremely unusual); 7) human interest (emotional background); 8) timeliness (novelty, freshness); 9) proximity (local issues). [2, p. 205]. News is not a genre in journalism, but it represents an objective category with its own properties and qualitative features. The news can be presented in any information genre if it does not contradict its main property, novelty. News is a prompt and relevant message for the audience, transmitted through mass media channels, about new facts, events, phenomena, processes from nature around us, and social reality. The selection of news depends on the culture and mentality of a given society, the type of journalism system, the type of media, and the priority agendas in that society at a given time [1, p. 152].

News in Medialinguistics

Recognizing the key importance of news texts in the overall mass media discourse system, researchers accept taking into account the following factors: Firstly, in every media outlet, news materials are characterized by stable format features. In the print media, news is represented by a fairly wide range of texts published on newspaper pages and magazine pages under the general heading “news”. They include news bulletins, news in briefs, and reports of correspondents. Also, they are organized in a certain thematic sequence: home news, international news, and business news. At the level of macrostructure, a news text, entirely designed in the form of a newspaper strip, radio, television program, or Internet news feed, consists of individual messages, each of which can be expanded to one degree or another [4, p. 53].

The term “format”, often used in relation to the sphere of mass media, means a stable combination of formal features of a media text with a certain content. By the format of a television channel, the format of a radio program, or the format of a magazine, they mean precisely the stable combination of certain external features with stable components of content and style. Thus, the concept of “format” is especially important since news texts have a carefully developed, highly organized, and extremely

stable structure, which, in combination with stable features at the language level, allows us to consider these texts as globally clichéd mass media texts [4, p. 55].

As mentioned above, news texts are characterized by a stable structure. Thus, most news texts in the press are built on the principle known in English-language journalism as “the inverted pyramid”. The concept of the inverted pyramid assumes that all the most valuable and important information is placed at the beginning of the text, where the main information load falls on the first phrase, which is called “the lead” and actually contains all the most important components of the message. As the text unfolds, the information load gradually weakens. That is a reader- and editor-friendly solution, because the reader may get the news from the beginning and decide whether to read details or not. Also, the editor may shorten the news text if it is required by removing some paragraphs from the end without damaging the content [4, p. 56].

Secondly, news texts have some syntactical and morphological features that show their qualities as dynamic, informative, striving for objectivity, and having a neutral style of presentation. In terms of structure or morphosyntax, basic features of a news text include the following: a significant number of verb phrases compared to other types of media texts; wide use of passive forms and impersonal structures; the linguistic economy principle; the presence of stable text-forming elements—linking phrases, links to the source of information, text-formatting phrases, including quotations [4, p. 62]. Thirdly, analysis of news texts at the lexical and phraseological level allows us to identify the following characteristic features: the texts are mostly filled with all types of clichéd phrases; absence of connotative phrases, with the exception of phrases with a political evaluative component; limited use of idiomatic compounds, concentrated mainly in citation contexts; the presence of a large number of culture-specific phrases, the understanding of which requires appropriate background knowledge or the presence of certain information of an extra-linguistic nature; use of phrases marked in terms of the ideological modality category; and conveying the ideological shade of the text [4, p. 68–71].

Conclusion

According to mediallynguistics, news is described as a special type of text that has a strict structure and format (as an example, “the inverted pyramid” structure of written news text), as well as some lexical, syntactical, and morphological features that distinguish news text from other media text types, like features, add, etc. Whereas, for

journalism, every piece of information that has novelty is news, no matter its form or genre type. It means that novelty could be found in every report written in the form of an article, a brief report, or an interview. Consequently, mediallynguistics helps to shape the linguistic features and format of news texts as a specific form of media text. On the other hand, the object of journalism in the definition of news is to find out the criteria for information that has novelty and can be defined as news. Both of these points of view give us a more comprehensive understanding of news texts. To sum up, news text is the text that covers information that has news value and gives a message in a strict format according to the media channel type (journal, radio, TV), using some specific structures, clichés, and other lexical units that differ from other types of media texts.

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